

***Vertical demos over Common large scale field Trials
for Rail, energy and media Industries***

5G-VIOS User Manual

**This project has received funding from the European Union's Framework Programme
Horizon 2020 for research, technological development and demonstration**

5G PPP Research and Validation of critical technologies and systems

Project Start Date: 1st June 2019

Duration: 49 months

Call: H2020-ICT-2019

Date of delivery: September 2023

Topic: ICT-19-2019

Version 1.0

Project co-funded by the European Commission

Under the H2020 programme

Dissemination Level: **Public**

Grant Agreement Number:	857201
Project Name:	Vertical demos over Common large scale field Trials for Rail, energy and media Industries
Project Acronym:	5G-VICTORI
Document Number:	-
Document Title:	5G-VIOS User Manual
Version:	1.0
Delivery Date:	<u>September 2023</u>
Responsible:	Digital Catapult (DCAT) Kostas Katsaros (DCAT)
Editor(s) & Authors:	Konstantinos Antonakoglou (DCAT) Mark Rouse (DCAT)
Keywords:	MANO, 5G-VIOS, Multi-Domain Orchestration, OSM, ONAP, Service Brokering, Service Orchestration, CI/CD, APIs, OSM
Status:	Final
Dissemination Level	Public
Project URL:	https://www.5g-victori-project.eu/

Table of Contents

1	INTRODUCTION	7
1.1	Open Source Technologies	7
1.2	5G-VIOS Public Release	7
1.3	Organisation of the document	7
2	INSTALLATION AND SETUP	8
2.1	Initial Setup	8
2.1.1	Minimum Software Components	8
2.1.2	Upload Ubuntu/Vyos Images to OpenStack	8
2.1.3	Setup your Control Host (CH)	8
2.2	Using the Automated Installation Framework (AIF)	9
2.2.1	Playbooks	9
2.2.2	Secrets	9
2.2.3	OpenStack	9
2.2.4	Group Variables	9
2.3	Running the Playbooks	10
2.3.1	Apply Cloud Environment Variables	11
2.3.2	Build the main 5G-VIOS Kubernetes Cluster	11
2.3.3	Build the Vyos Hub Node	11
2.3.4	Build the Vyos Spoke Node for your Edge	11
2.3.5	Build your Edge or the EdgeProxy	11
2.4	Configuring Vyos Router	11
2.4.1	Enabling Ethernet and ssh on Vyos Hub/Spoke	11
2.4.2	Enabling the HTTPS APIs	12
3	REGISTERING EDGES	13
3.1	Using the Edge Registration Form	13
3.2	Uploading an Edge Descriptor to Register a new Edge	13
3.3	Inter-Facility Requirements	14
4	CREATING EXPERIMENTS	15
4.1	Using the Experiment Creation Form	15
4.2	Uploading an Experiment Descriptor to create a new Experiment	16
5	INSTANTIATING EXPERIMENTS	18
5.1	Onboarding NSDs/VNFs Packages into OSM	18
5.2	Deploying Experiments in 5G-VIOS	20
5.2.1	Initiate Phase	20

5.2.2 Deploy Phase 20

6 ACRONYMS 21

List of Figures

Figure 2-1: Example all.yaml configuration file.....	10
Figure 3-1: Registering a new Edge Form.....	13
Figure 3-2: Uploading an Edge Descriptor.	14
Figure 3-3: Edge Descriptor JSON Example.....	14
Figure 4-1: Creating an Experiment Form	15
Figure 4-2: Uploading an Experiment Descriptor.	16
Figure 4-3: Experiment Descriptor JSON Example	17
Figure 5-1: VNFD yaml Package Example.....	19
Figure 5-2: NSD yaml Package Example	20
Figure 5-3: Instantiating an Experiment.....	20

List of Tables

Table 1-1: Open Source Technologies.....	7
Table 1-2: Public Release Repositories	7
Table 2-1: Minimum Software Package Versioning.	8
Table 2-2: Control Host Components.	8
Table 2-3: Automation Playbooks.....	9
Table 2-4: Playbook Variables.....	10
Table 3-1: Edge Registration Form Field Names.	13
Table 4-1: Creating an Experiment Form Field Names.....	15

1 Introduction

The 5G-VICTORI Infrastructure Operating System (5G-VIOS) is an inter-domain network service orchestration platform that allows users to automatically deploy virtualised applications across common cloud infrastructure. A more technical discussion on, and the design off, 5G-VIOS can be found in the publicly available deliverables **D2.5**, and **D2.6** located at <https://www.5g-victori-project.eu/project-outcomes/deliverables/>.

The purpose of this document is to convey how to install and use 5G-VIOS to automate the deployment of network services.

1.1 Open Source Technologies

5G-VIOS utilises several publicly available open source technologies. These technologies are outlined in Table 1-1.

Table 1-1: Open Source Technologies

Technology	URL
OpenStack	https://www.openstack.org/
OSM	https://osm.etsi.org/
Kubernetes	https://kubernetes.io/
Helm	https://helm.sh/
Vyos Router	https://vyos.io/
Python	https://www.python.org/

1.2 5G-VIOS Public Release

5G-VIOS is released to the public through various repositories. Docker Hub is used as the container library to host Docker images for each of the 5G-VIOS' microservices. Helm is used to install each microservice, and GitHub hosts a set of Helm charts to aid in the installation of 5G-VIOS. To automate the installation and provisioning of 5G-VIOS, a special infrastructure repository provides automation playbooks that allow the installation and configuration of key assets as part of the 5G-VIOS ecosystem. URLs for these repositories are provided in Table 1-2.

Table 1-2: Public Release Repositories

Repository	URL
Docker Images	https://hub.docker.com/search?q=digicatapult
Helm Charts	https://github.com/5G-VICTORI-project/vios-helmcharts
Infrastructure Scripts	https://github.com/5G-VICTORI-project/vios-infra

1.3 Organisation of the document

This document comprises six sections. Following the Introduction:

- Section 2 is a functional walkthrough in using the infrastructure provision playbooks to automatically install and configure 5G-VIOS.
- Section 3 describes how to register new edges or domain within 5G-VIOS.
- Section 4 introduces the concept of experiments which are used to deploy a collection of one or more network services for a given application.
- Section 5 explains how to deploy your experiment.
- Finally, Section 6 lists acronyms used throughout this document.

2 Installation and Setup

This section details the process of installing 5G-VIOS and other components.

2.1 Initial Setup

2.1.1 Minimum Software Components

To install 5G-VIOS, several software packages are required, and their minimal versions are outlined below in Table 2-1.

Table 2-1: Minimum Software Package Versioning.

Component	Minimum Version
OpenStack	Wallaby
OSM	v10
Kubernetes	v1.21.3-00
Helm	v3.11.0
Vyos Router	v1-4-rolling

2.1.2 Upload Ubuntu/Vyos Images to OpenStack

You will also need to upload images to OpenStack for Ubuntu 22.04 server, and for Vyos Router.

2.1.3 Setup your Control Host (CH)

To run the 5G-VIOS Automation Installation Framework (AIF), you need to have a device with Internet access that will act as your Control Host (CH). The CH will need the following components installed as prerequisites:

Table 2-2: Control Host Components.

Component	Minimum Version
Openstack SDK	v0.61.0
Ansible	v2.14.1
Decorator	v5.1.1
Git	v2.41.0
Python	v3.9.x

You will first need to use Git to clone a copy of the public 5G-VIOS Infrastructure Repository, located at the url: <https://github.com/5G-VICTORI-project/vios-infra>, to your CH. From a terminal window on your CH, run the following command:

```
git clone git@github.com:5G-VICTORI-project/vios-infra.git
```

This will create a **vios-infra** folder on your CH, whereby you will find the playbooks and scripts of the AIF. Next, you will need to install Python on your CH. Once Python is installed, you then need to install the necessary Python libraries, using the **requirements.txt** file provided. To use Python’s package manager, PIP, to install the required libraries, run the following command from a terminal window:

```
pip install -r requirements.txt
```

Once these components are installed you are ready to use the AIF.

2.2 Using the Automated Installation Framework (AIF)

Currently, the AIF only supports the use of OpenStack as your cloud provider for building the necessary virtual infrastructure for 5G-VIOS.

2.2.1 Playbooks

The playbooks use Ansible as the automation platform, and are outlined as shown in Table 2-3:

Table 2-3: Automation Playbooks.

Playbook	Description
<code>vios-multi-node-cluster-playbook</code>	Builds a three node VIOS production cluster
<code>vios-single-node-cluster-playbook</code>	Builds a single node VIOS development cluster
<code>vyos-hub-playbook</code>	Builds the Vios Hub node
<code>edge-with-osm-edgeproxy-playbook</code>	Builds an edge node with OSM and the EdgeProxy installed
<code>edgeproxy-only-playbook</code>	Builds a single node with just the EdgeProxy installed
<code>vyos-spoke-playbook</code>	Builds a Vios Spoke node

2.2.2 Secrets

Create a new file in your home directory to store secret environment variables:

```
mkdir ~/.secrets
touch ~/.secrets/ansible
```

In the ansible file you just created, set the following environment variables, replacing `((value))` with your own corresponding values, and save the file:

```
export CLOUD_SERVER=((value))
export CLOUD_USERNAME=((value))
export CLOUD_PASSWORD=((value))
export CLOUD_AUTH_URL=((value))
export CLOUD_TENANT_NAME=((value))
```

2.2.3 OpenStack

For your given cloud tenant to run the playbooks against, you will also need to download to your home directory your OpenStack RC (Identity API v3) file, which you can do from Horizon. You will also need to create a key pair. In Horizon, you can either create a new key pair, or upload the public key of an existing key pair. Name your key pair as ansible.

2.2.4 Group Variables

Global variables for all playbooks are set in a single place located in a file called `all.yaml`, and outlined below in Table 2-4.

Table 2-4: Playbook Variables.

Variable	Description
app_node_image	The base image to use to build your 5G-VIOS nodes
app_node_base_flavor_name	The resources flavour to use for support nodes
app_node_key_flavor_name	The resources flavour to use for key 5G-VIOS nodes
app_node_region	The cloud region to use for 5G-VIOS nodes
app_node_az	The cloud availability zone to use for 5G-VIOS nodes
app_remote_user	The remote ssh user to use to access your 5G-VIOS nodes
app_network	The cloud network to attach your 5G-VIOS nodes to
app_sec_group	The cloud security group to attach your 5G-VIOS nodes to
cloud_key	The cloud api key to use for secure access
cloud_net_provider	The cloud network provider name, default set to provider
osm_version	The version of OSM you are using
edge_name	The name to be given as an identifier for an edge
edge_vlan_range_start	The starting vlan pool range for your edge, default set to 0
edge_vlan_range_end	The ending vlan pool range for your edge, default set to 0
vyos_image_name	This is the name of the image to use to build Vynos hub/spoke nodes

These variables need to be set before you can run the AIF. An example of the `all.yaml` variables being correctly set is given at figure 2-1, and should match your own values depending on your instance.

```

app_node_image: ubuntu-20.04-server-amd64
app_node_base_flavor_name: "4.8.80"
app_node_key_flavor_name: "4.8.80"
app_node_region: RegionOne
app_node_az: nova
app_remote_user: ubuntu
app_network: "5G-VICTORI Mgmt"
app_sec_group: default
cloud_key: ansible
cloud_net_provider: provider
osm_version: 13
edge_name: nomadic
edge_vlan_range_start: 0
edge_vlan_range_end: 0
vyos_image_name: vyos-14-persistent

```

Figure 2-1: Example all.yaml configuration file.

2.3 Running the Playbooks

The playbooks are designed to be run in a specific order to help with the automation of installing 5G-VIOS.

2.3.1 Apply Cloud Environment Variables

Open a new terminal. Set up the environment variables for your OpenStack environment by running the following command, replacing **((file))** with your OpenStack RC file, and enter the password when prompted:

```
source ((file))
```

2.3.2 Build the main 5G-VIOS Kubernetes Cluster

At this stage, you can either build a three node production cluster, or a single node development cluster for 5G-VIOS. Run the following shell script to build a production cluster:

```
./setup_vios_multi_node_cluster.sh
```

Or, for a development cluster, run:

```
./setup_vios_single_node_cluster.sh
```

2.3.3 Build the Vyos Hub Node

Next, you will need to build the Vyos Hub node, which you can do by running the following shell script:

```
./setup_vyos_hub.sh
```

2.3.4 Build the Vyos Spoke Node for your Edge

Before you can build your edge, you first need to set up the Vyos Spoke node for your edge. To do this, run the following shell script (making sure you have given your edge a name in the **all.yaml** file):

```
./setup_vyos_spoke.sh
```

2.3.5 Build your Edge or the EdgeProxy

When building your edge, there are two choices. You can either build a fully integrated edge with OSM and the EdgeProxy, or if you already have OSM set up, you can build a separate EdgeProxy node. To build a fully integrated edge with OSM and the EdgeProxy, run the following shell script:

```
./setup_edge.sh
```

Or, to build a separate EdgeProxy node, run the following shell script:

```
./setup_edgeproxy_only.sh
```

2.4 Configuring Vyos Router

As the base public Vyos Router image ships with Ethernet and ssh down, manual configuration of Vyos is needed. The following steps need to be applied to the Hub and all edge Spokes in your instance.

2.4.1 Enabling Ethernet and ssh on Vyos Hub/Spoke

From the OpenStack console of your Vyos Router virtual machine, log into Vyos and run the following commands, where **((ip address))** is the IP address of the Vyos Router virtual machine:

```
config
set interface ethernet eth0 address ((ip address))/24
```

```
set interface ethernet eth0 address dhcp
set service ssh
Save && commit
```

You should now be able to ssh into this VM.

2.4.2 Enabling the HTTPS APIs

Either continue in your OpenStack console, or ssh into you Vynos Router VM, enable https by running the following commands to active Vynos' API interface:

```
config
set service https api keys id demo_id key demo_key
set service https api debug
set service https api port 8080
save && commit
```

3 Registering Edges

This section describes the process of registering new inter-domains or edges with 5G-VIOS. There are two ways of registering an edge, either via the registration form, or uploading an edge descriptor.

3.1 Using the Edge Registration Form

The Edge Registration form has several fields that need input to successfully register a new edge in 5G-VIOS, as exemplified in Figure 3-1.

Figure 3-1: Registering a new Edge Form

These fields are further described below in Table 3-1.

Table 3-1: Edge Registration Form Field Names.

Field Name	Field Description
Name	The given name of the Edge
IP Address	The IP address of the Edge
Edge Port	A default port for the Edge’s Edge Proxy microservice
NSD Catalog	A redundant field and will be removed in a future release
VNFD Catalog	A redundant field and will be removed in a future release
Switch ID	A redundant field and will be removed in a future release
Switch Port	A redundant field and will be removed in a future release
VLAN Pool Min-Max	The range of vlans that the Edge supports
Edge Longitude, Latitude & Radius	The longitude, latitude, and radius of the Edge

3.2 Uploading an Edge Descriptor to Register a new Edge

Alternatively, a JSON formatted file can be used to upload a predefined edge descriptor by selecting **File** from the drop down menu, and click on **Choose File**, as exemplified below.

Figure 3-2: Uploading an Edge Descriptor.

The Edge Descriptor must have a specific set of fields defined, as exemplified in Figure 3-3.

```
{
  "edge_name": "Demo_Edge",
  "edge_ip_address": "10.10.100.18",
  "edge_port": "30001",
  "edge_switch_id": 0,
  "edge_switch_port": 0,
  "edge_vlan_pool_min": 160,
  "edge_vlan_pool_max": 175,
  "edge_longitude": 0,
  "edge_latitude": 0,
  "edge_radius": 0,
  "edge_create_user": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6"
}
```

Figure 3-3: Edge Descriptor JSON Example

3.3 Inter-Facility Requirements

To register an edge in another subnet or domain, 5G-VIOS needs to be able to communicate with that edge across the Internet. This can be best achieved by setting up a site-to-site VPN connection between the OpenStack environment where 5G-VIOS is installed, and the OpenStack environment where your remote edge is setup. A site-to-site VPN connection can then provide an always active connection between different facilities.

4 Creating Experiments

This section describes the process of creating new experiments with 5G-VIOS. There are two ways of creating new experiments, either via the create experiment form, or uploading an experiment descriptor.

4.1 Using the Experiment Creation Form

The Create Experiment form has several fields that need input to successfully register a new experiment in 5G-VIOS, as exemplified in Figure 4-1.

Figure 4-1: Creating an Experiment Form

These fields are further described below in Table 4-1.

Table 4-1: Creating an Experiment Form Field Names.

Field Name	Field Description
Name	The given name for the experiment
Type	The type of experiment
Network Services	The network services selected to be included in the experiment
DNS Names	A csv list of any DNS names that need to be included
Resources	Any compute resources to be included in the experiment
Network Services KPIs	Any network service KPIs to be included in the experiment
Application KPIs	Any application KPIs to be included in the experiment
Config	Any configuration settings to be included in the experiment
Use Profiling	Denotes if 5G-VIOS should use the Profiler to analyse KPIs in selecting optimal resources for your network services

4.2 Uploading an Experiment Descriptor to create a new Experiment

Alternatively, a JSON formatted file can be used to upload a predefined experiment descriptor by selecting **File** from the drop down menu, and click on **Choose File**, as exemplified in Figure 4-2.

Figure 4-2: Uploading an Experiment Descriptor.

The Experiment Descriptor must have a specific set of fields defined, as exemplified below.

```
{
  "Name": "Demo_App",
  "Type": "Standard",
  "Exclusive": true,
  "UEs": [
    "UE_1",
    "UE_2"
  ],
  "Scenario": "Scenario1",
  "Automated": true,
  "NSDIDs": [
    "18d44836-8400-4c4d-98ba-d667e3c09a24,52c07dcf-db56-463c-931f-c6f4234eca73,vios-edge-bdbf1",
    "48da164e-1fe0-4fe5-96f2-cced2235aa56,79e579a7-a0ce-4405-babf-140522c1d21d,vios-edge-bdbf2"
  ],
  "resources": {
    "cpu": {
      "min_cores": "2",
      "max_cores": "8"
    },
    "memory": {
      "min": "2000",
      "max": "10000"
    },
    "link_capacity": {
      "min": "400000000",
      "max": "1400000000"
    }
  },
  "ns_kpis": {
    "cpu_utilisation": 0.98,
    "memory_utilisation": 100
  },
}
```

```
"app_kpis": {  
  "latency": 3  
},  
"service_exp_dns": {  
  "ns": []  
},  
"service_exp_config": {  
  "ns": []  
},  
"service_profile_flag": false  
}
```

Figure 4-3: Experiment Descriptor JSON Example

5 Instantiating Experiments

This section describes how to successfully instantiate your experiments in 5G-VIOS. You must first onboard your application's network service(s) NSD and VNFD packages within OSM for each edge you wish to use.

5.1 Onboarding NSDs/VNFDs Packages into OSM

For your given edge, login into OSM, and create a new VNFD. You must first create your VNFD before you can create the associated NSD. An example of an VNFD is shown in Figure 5-1.

```
vnfd:
  id: democache_vnfd
  product-name: democache_vnfd
  description: Generated by OSM package generator
  provider: OSM
  version: '1.0'
  mgmt-cp: vnf-cp0-ext
  virtual-storage-desc:
    - id: democache_vnfd-VM-storage
      size-of-storage: 1
  virtual-compute-desc:
    - id: democache_vnfd-VM-compute
      virtual-cpu:
        num-virtual-cpu: 1
      virtual-memory:
        size: 1
  sw-image-desc:
    - id: "cirros"
      name: "cirros"
      image: "cirros"
  df:
    - id: default-df
      instantiation-level:
        - id: default-instantiation-level
          vdu-level:
            - vdu-id: democache_vnfd-VM
              number-of-instances: 1
  vdu-profile:
    - id: democache_vnfd-VM
      min-number-of-instances: 1
      max-number-of-instances: 1
  vdu:
    - id: democache_vnfd-VM
```

```

name: democache_vnfd-VM
description: democache_vnfd-VM
sw-image-desc: "cirros"
cloud-init-file: demo_init
virtual-storage-desc:
- democache_vnfd-VM-storage
virtual-compute-desc: democache_vnfd-VM-compute
int-cpd:
- id: eth0-int
  virtual-network-interface-requirement:
  - name: eth0
    virtual-interface:
      type: PARAVIRT
ext-cpd:
- id: vnf-cp0-ext
int-cpd:
  vdu-id: democache_vnfd-VM
  cpd: eth0-int

```

Figure 5-1: VNFD yaml Package Example

Next, create you NSD. An example NSD is shown in Figure 5-2.

```

nsd:
  nsd:
  - id: democache_nsd
    name: democache_nsd
    designer: dc
    description: Generated by OSM package generator
    version: '1.0'
    vnfd-id:
    - democache_vnfd
  df:
  - id: default-df
    vnf-profile:
    - id: "1"
      vnfd-id: democache_vnfd
    virtual-link-connectivity:
    - virtual-link-profile-id: mgmt
      constituent-cpd-id:
      - constituent-base-element-id: "1"
        constituent-cpd-id: vnf-cp0-ext

```

```
virtual-link-desc:
- id: mgmt
  mgmt-network: true
```

Figure 5-2: NSD yaml Package Example

5.2 Deploying Experiments in 5G-VIOS

To start the instantiate process, simply click on the button from the **Manage Experiment** screen to start the deployment of your experiment and network service(s).

Figure 5-3: Instantiating an Experiment

5.2.1 Initiate Phase

The first stage of deployment is the **Initiate** phase. 5G-VIOS will assess if the appropriate resources are available at the respective edge(s) to ensure your network service(s) can be deployed.

5.2.2 Deploy Phase

If resources are available at your selected edge(s), then 5G-VIOS we begin to automatically configure your Vios Router Hub/Spoke VMs to build a Dynamic Multi-point VPN (DMVPN) transport network necessary to allow your network services to communicate with each other in a secure manner.

6 Acronyms

Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
CH	Control Host
DMVPN	Dynamic Multi-point VPN
JSON	Java Script Object Notation
NSD	Network Service Descriptor
OSM	Open Source Mano
VM	Virtual Machine
VNFD	Virtual Network Function Descriptor
VPN	Virtual Private Network